

1 **Supplemental Materials for “Modeling Long-Term Flow Regimes in**
2 **Ungauged Basins: An Evaluation of Machine Learning Performance and**
3 **Uncertainty”**

4 **Supplement 2: Environmental Descriptor Details**

5 immediate

6 **ENVIRONMENTAL DESCRIPTOR DETAILS**

7 • Climate

8 Climate-related variables such as precipitation, temperature, evapotranspiration, and potential
9 evapotranspiration were normalized to monthly averages from 2001 to 2020 for each river basin,
10 using minimum, maximum, and average values. Precipitation was sourced from the Integrated
11 Multi-Satellite Retrievals for the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission (IMERG),
12 a product of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and Japan Aerospace
13 Exploration Agency (JAXA) (Huffman et al. 2020). IMERG provides high-resolution global
14 precipitation estimates, combining data from satellites such as the Tropical Rainfall Measuring
15 Mission (TRMM) (Huffman et al. 2007) and the GPM mission (Skofronick-Jackson et al. 2017).
16 Land surface temperature (T), evapotranspiration (ET), and potential evapotranspiration (PET)
17 were collected from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) products (Mu
18 et al. 2007; Mu et al. 2011), derived from the Terra and Aqua satellites. These variables play a
19 significant role in water-loss processes and are key to understanding streamflow responses in basins.

20 • Water Storage

21 Different components of water storage, such as groundwater, soil moisture, surface water, and
22 reservoir water, were also included in the list of environmental descriptors, with data collection
23 methods detailed in [Barbedo et al. 2022a](#). Total water storage data were derived from the Gravity
24 Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) and its follow-up mission GRACE-FO, which measure
25 changes in Earth's gravity field due to water mass distribution shifts ([Landerer et al. 2020](#); [Tapley
26 et al. 2004](#)). Reservoir storage information came from the Brazilian National Interconnected System
27 (SIN), providing insights into reservoir capacities and water levels ([ANA 2021](#)). Surface water
28 storage data were acquired from the South America MGB model (MGB-SA), a physically based
29 framework that simulates the hydrological cycle of Brazilian river basins and includes rivers, lakes,
30 and wetlands ([Siqueira et al. 2018](#)), which reported accuracy of Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE)
31 > 0.6 in 55% of the evaluated cases for daily discharge and water levels. Soil moisture data were
32 sourced from the Global Land Data Assimilation System (GLDAS), which assimilates various data
33 to estimate soil moisture globally, particularly in the root zone ([Rodell et al. 2004](#)).

- 34 • Lithology, Soils, and Land Cover

35 The categorical variables belonging to the domains of lithology, soils, and land cover were
36 collected based on the percentage of occupancy of each class within basin boundaries. Variables
37 related to soil content were numerical (water, organic matter, clay, silt, and sand contents), which
38 were averaged over basin areas. Lithology classes came from the Global Lithological Map (GLiM)
39 database ([Hartmann and Moosdorf 2012](#)). This database, at a 50 km resolution, obtains geological
40 information from various sources to categorize the Earth's surface into ten lithological classes,
41 including sedimentary, volcanic, plutonic, and metamorphic rocks, and unconsolidated deposits.
42 Soil properties were sourced from the OpenLandMap database ([Hengl et al. 2017](#)). This database
43 consists of detailed global soil information at 250 m resolution, including texture, organic matter
44 content, and pH, using a blend of soil maps and modeling. For land-cover classes, data from
45 the Mapbiomas database ([Souza et al. 2020](#)) were used for Brazilian territory, and the MODIS
46 dataset ([Friedl and Sulla-Menashe 2019](#)) was used for the remaining areas. The original land-cover

47 classes from both databases were simplified into five categories: forests, grasslands, agriculture,
48 semi-permeable regions, and water bodies, facilitating cross-regional analysis and comparison.

- 49 • Geomorphology

50 Geomorphological variables were considered here as all variables derived from a digital ele-
51 vation model (DEM); some require minimal processing, such as elevation and slope, and others
52 require more complex procedures, such as drainage-network and terrain-class attribution. Elevation
53 and slope data for each river basin, including averages and standard deviations, were obtained from
54 the MERIT-DEM product (Yamazaki et al. 2017), which consists of a DEM with approximately 90
55 m resolution, derived by correcting vegetation-height errors from other DEM datasets.

56 For drainage-dependent information, we first extracted a stream mask using the topographic
57 position-based stream definition (TPS) (Barbedo et al. 2022b) on the MERIT-DEM and MERIT-
58 Hydro (Yamazaki et al. 2019) datasets, with the universal parameters recommended by the authors
59 of the method. As drainage density has been demonstrated to have great influence on flow conditions
60 (Dingman 1978; Gregory and Walling 1968; Price et al. 2011), a consistent map that accurately
61 represents its spatial variability could have a great influence on the flow estimations in this study.
62 The TPS method was preferred over traditional methods for drainage extraction from DEMs, which
63 typically rely on a uniform drainage-area threshold, because the variability in drainage density over
64 large heterogeneous regions is not properly addressed by the latter; and over the vector drainage
65 network provided by the Ottocodified Hydrological Database (BHO) dataset, because digitized
66 vector networks from field surveys are prone to inconsistencies due to human interpretation and
67 survey quality, resulting in mismatches between adjacent maps or regions, whereas TPS applies a
68 consistent set of parameters across the entire DEM map, ensuring uniformity in drainage-network
69 extraction across regions with varying topography.

70 From the combination of the derived drainage and the DEM grids, a height above nearest
71 drainage (HAND) map was created (Nobre et al. 2011; Rennó et al. 2008). A categorical terrain

72 map was then computed from HAND and slope by applying fixed raster-classification rules:

$$73 \quad \text{class} = \begin{cases} \text{wetland,} & \text{HAND} < 5 \text{ m,} \\ \text{hillslope,} & \text{HAND} \geq 5 \text{ m and slope} > 10\%, \\ \text{plateau,} & \text{HAND} \geq 5 \text{ m and slope} \leq 10\%. \end{cases}$$

74 This classification is based on studies linking terrain and drainage attributes to hydrological response
75 (e.g. [Gao et al. 2014](#); [Gharari et al. 2011](#); [Savenije 2010](#)), where wetlands represent low areas close
76 to the drainage network, hillslopes represent steeper areas associated with faster water movement,
77 and plateaus represent higher and flatter areas where groundwater recharge is more present.

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